

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FROM EQUATIONS TO AUTHENTIC SOLUTIONS: EXPLORING THE ROLE OF PBL IN MATH

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Abstract

This research examines the implementation of Project-Based Learning (PBL) in high school mathematics class and its impact on learners' problem-solving skills. By employing qualitative research method via focus group interviews among 10th grade students, one-on-one interview with math teacher, classroom observations, and curriculum and syllabus analysis, this paper scrutinizes the consistency of math curriculum in local Azerbaijani school with the major PBL principles. Results show that while real-life applications of math topics and collaborative learning opportunities are evident in the local math curriculum, traditional teaching methods and exam-centeredness still prevail in classroom instructions. Yet the results also reveal that although PBL elements incorporated into math classes have fragmented character, they develop learners' critical thinking, creativity, problem solving skills and increase the level of motivation. The study emphasizes the need for curriculum improvements and teacher professional development opportunities to systematically integrate PBL in mathematics in the future.

Keywords: problem/project-based learning, mathematics, problem-solving skills, high school.

Introduction

The most popular and effective teaching and learning approach which is more contextual, competence-based, and student oriented is Project/Problem-Based Learning (PBL) extensively employed in educational institutions in many Western countries. PBL, which puts the learners in the center of the education process and makes them responsible for their own learning, thereby contributing to deeper understanding and greater retention of content knowledge is considered as a relatively innovative teaching method. The teaching philosophy of PBL is based on constructivist theory, which highlights the importance of learning that occurs in connection with the real world. Educational philosophers John Dewey and his student William Killpatrick emphasized the positive impact of real-life practice in formal education. However, as Dewey states, not all practices and experiences are educative. He claims that traditional teaching models also include some kind of experience; yet they mainly impede the development of further experiences, which is the actual problem. Hence, children in the traditional classrooms are not prevented from having any experience entirely, rather they face a wrong form of it from the standpoint of not preparing them for the situations outside of the classroom and depriving them of the capacity of evaluating and acting appropriately in the new circumstances (Dewey, 1938; Killpatrick, 1918). Dewey's educational philosophy promotes the idea that teaching lesson topics in relation to their real-life application not only enhances the understanding of the subject matter but also helps to realize the economic and industrial issues of a contemporary society.

As a systematic method of instruction, PBL first started to be implemented in McMaster University in Canada in medical education and very soon proved to

be a successful approach in terms of facilitating students' motivation, problem solving, and autonomous learning skills (Borhan & Yassin, 2013; Krishnan, 2009). The success of PBL in medical education paved the way to other fields as well, eventually resulting in the intensive use of it in engineering, science, business education, and other disciplines across the world (Strobel & Barneveld, 2009). PBL driven classes comprise common main learning principles, such as real-life problems, teamwork, self-directed and student-centered learning (Kolmos, Holgaard, & Dahl, 2013). The six main components included in PBL approach, such as learner-centeredness, group collaboration, authentic problems, teacher role as a facilitator, self-directed learning, and problem-solving skills (Barrows, 1996) promote learner motivation, autonomy, and active learning.

Although a considerable number of studies were conducted to examine the implementation of PBL in teaching different subjects in schools across various countries, it remains one of the focal points to consider in the educational transformation process. As the concentration of the modern labor market has shifted to search for graduates who are equipped with the skills that match the current demand of industries, it is crucial to scrutinize different aspects of PBL implementation in specific disciplines with attention on the development of 21st century skills. Thus, the purpose of this research is to analyze the experience of PBL implementation in high school mathematics classes. The study was guided by the following research question: How can PBL be implemented in high school math classes and how can its implementation impact high school math students' problem-solving skills?

The Significance of the Study

Azerbaijan, as one of the post-Soviet countries has been undergoing fundamental changes for the last several decades in its political, economic, and particularly, education systems. Because of being a part of the Soviet education system for many years, the curriculum of the educational institutions in the country were predominantly teacher-oriented, and instruction methods focused merely on theoretical knowledge acquisition, memorization, and teaching for testing rather than skill development (Mammadova, 2020). Therefore, with the purpose to transform the old system so that to meet the demands of the contemporary society, after gaining independence, Azerbaijani government took crucial steps in different levels of education. One of the primary reasons behind this reform process is the existing skill mismatch between the labor market and the current education system in the country. The mismatch is evident mainly in the higher order cognitive and socio-behavioral skills of young people (Amirova & Valiyev, 2021). This fact necessitated relevant policy changes to foster the country's education system at all levels.

Amending the general education curriculum, which comprises of primary (grades 1-4), lower secondary (grades 5-9), and full secondary education (grades 10-11) was one of the major steps taken forward in the process of educational transformation. The

first stage in the policy level was the enactment of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Education in 2009. The Law emphasizes the importance of cultivating competitive specialists needed not only in local but also in international labor markets. The need to possess systematized theoretical and practical knowledge alongside the skills and competences is highlighted in the Law (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on education, 2009, Articles 4.0.2., 4.0.3., 9.2., 11.1.11.1.2.).

As seen from the table, the Azerbaijani government accentuates the incorporation of critical thinking, decision making, autonomous learning, problem solving and other soft skills into the school curriculum. Since PBL is a teaching method which involves students in active learning process through solving meaningful real-life problems and which helps them acquire critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication skills, the integration of this method into the teaching process in schools seems as the most relevant step towards the paradigm shift in education.

When it comes specifically to the competences and skills essential to develop in math classes in full secondary education, State Standards of General Education underline as follows (Article 10.4.6.) (See Table 1):

Table 1.

Competence to develop in math classes at a full secondary education level.

Full Secondary Education (grades 10-11)	
Mathematics	makes algorithms and evaluates the outcomes
	uses functional dependence and their various expressions in problem solving
	uses spatial perceptions in the creation of various visuals
	explains the regularities in the surrounding world based on probability and statistics, calculates the probability of the events, and forecasts their occurrences
	justifies assumptions with mathematical evidence and distinguishes the proven suggestion from the hypothetical one

Mathematics is a subject which actively involves learners in the process of problem solving. It is at the same time a subject which is mainly considered among learners to be a boring one. There can be various factors affecting student disengagement in math classes, such as rigid teaching methodology, overreliance on textbooks, incompetence of teachers in making connection of the math topics to the real world and many others. Furthermore, students cannot model any physical, chemical, or real-life processes in math or cannot express any process in math language then analyze the model and verify how his or her model works properly on their own. Since problem solving stands at the core of math and is emphasized as one of the major 21st century skills and labor market demands, it is crucial to examine the possible ways of restructuring math classes to foster maximum student engagement, which in turn will most likely contribute to the increased problem-solving skills of young learners. Furthermore, the skills acquired in math classes directly affect learners' performance in other disciplines, such as chemistry, biology, physics, geography, as well as humanities and social

sciences. Hence, scrutinizing the existing studies related to various effective approaches in math teaching, specifically, with the focus on students' problem-solving ability may add insights into the body of knowledge and identify the ways making mathematics classes more engaging and connected to the real world.

Methodology

The current study applied a qualitative research method for data collection employing focus group interviews, classroom observations, individual interview, and document analysis as the main research tools. The participants for focus groups were chosen via purposeful sampling method because the researchers wanted to develop a detailed understanding of the PBL concept (Cresswell, 2012). The rationale behind utilizing focus group interviews was to collect shared perspectives from different individuals and at the same time from specific people. The sample size in this study is twenty (n=20) 10th grade students out of overall one hundred thirty-five (N=135) 10th grade student population in one of the local schools in the capital city, Baku. Since it is typical for qualitative research to study few individuals or sites (Creswell, 2012), the current research aimed at providing in-depth perspectives of the chosen sample.

Ten (10) of the students were females and ten (10) were males. Overall, four focus group interviews consisting of five representatives in each were conducted. The advantage of focus group interviews for this study was that during the interaction among interviewees, the researchers could identify critical perspectives regarding the studied concept (Cresswell, 2012). Interviews covered a two-week period in the middle of May 2024.

The researchers also utilized non-participant observations of 10th grade math classes in the sample school in the beginning of May 2024 aiming at collecting the information directly from the natural setting. The class was informed in advance that non-participant observation would be conducted for research purposes. Field notes were written in the observation protocol form. The researchers took descriptive notes about the step-by-step process of the class and focused specifically on the use of different interaction patterns, student autonomy, the use of real-life examples and problems in the explanation and solution of math concepts.

Additionally, to gain deeper insight into the possibilities of incorporating PBL in math classes, an individual semi-structured interview was conducted with the math teacher. A total of ten (10) questions were prepared in advance. Yet, based on the answers, follow-up questions were also asked. All of them were open-ended and were designed to learn the perspective of the teacher regarding the possibilities and challenges of using real life applications of math concepts in the classes. The informed consent form was sent to the respondent prior to the interview and was signed and returned. The interview was tape recorded with the consent of the teacher and lasted for approximately forty-five minutes. The answers were transcribed by the researchers and validated by the interviewee to avoid any misinterpretation of the ideas. The responses were coded using a lean coding approach, and relevant categories and themes were identified.

As another tool, the analysis of documents was undertaken to identify the math concepts included in the curriculum and see whether they were favorable to teach using PBL method. Math curriculum and the course syllabus were scrutinized for this purpose. According to the documents, 10th grade students in the sample school learn math foundations (natural numbers, fractions, percentages, real numbers, algebraic fractions, polynomials, radical expressions, one variable equation, inequalities, system of equations, initial concepts of geometry, triangles), divisions of polynomials and probability and statistics in fall term. In Spring term, the students learn triangles, type and properties of triangles, sequence and series, quadrilaterals and polygons, functions, their graphs and properties, trigonometric ratio, unit circle, identities and trigonometric equations.

Results

The purpose of the research was to examine the possibility of the implementation of PBL as a teaching methodology in math classes and its impact on high school students' problem-solving skills.

The analysis of the math curriculum and course syllabus reveals that the purpose of the course is aligned

with the Law on Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan and State Standards of General Education regarding cultivating highly intellectual solution providers who can effectively communicate and collaborate not only in the local but also in the global community. The scrutiny of the course syllabus also displays that teaching methodology in math classes is not only a classical approach where most of the content is delivered and practiced under the direct supervision of a teacher. Math modelling, which is defined in the document as a process of translating the real-world problems into mathematical expression and interpreting the results in the light of the original problem, aims at developing the learners higher order thinking skills, such as questioning, evaluating and analyzing. Problem-based learning approach is also highlighted in the course syllabus as a supplement to traditional direct method, which in turn has the purpose to foster higher-order thinking skills, as well as teamwork, collaboration, communication, presentation and other 21st century competences. Regarding the math topics covered in the course, it can be said that they are mostly favorable to be taught with PBL method. However, as seen from the document analysis, traditional instruction method is the dominating approach in math classes, and the course assessment is predominantly summative.

To have an in-depth understanding of the issue a one-on-one interview with the math teacher was conducted. From the interview, several opportunities and challenges related to PBL implementation in math classes were identified. As stated by the respondent, virtually all the topics that are included in high school math curriculum can be taught via PBL method, but especially functions topic and trigonometry fit perfectly well to real life application model. For example, modeling the motion of a ball using quadratic functions can be represented by the equation ($y = ax^2 + bx + c$, where a , b and c are real numbers and $a \neq 0$). With the help of this modeling process, students can understand that when the ball reaches the ground, this point corresponds to the x-intercept of the function. The maximum height of the ball and the time at which this height is reached are represented by the vertex of the parabola. As a PBL project, this math modeling can be employed for designing a tool that can help analyze and predict the success of basketball shots using quadratic functions. The outcome of the project can help the school basketball team to have more accurate shots. During the project implementation, the learners will collect data about the height of the ball and the angle and speed of the shot, which results in teams' demonstration of the best angles and velocities for the shots. By evaluating mathematical accuracy, practicality, creativity, and community involvement, the project may enhance student engagement and problem-solving skills.

Another example expressed by the interviewee was related to trigonometry. In this topic, students should understand that any circular or periodic process can be modeled using trigonometric functions, particularly sine or cosine, as shown in the equations ($y = a \sin bx + c$ or $y = a \cos bx + c$). While learning this, students should analyze the period by examining the

time interval between occurrences of maxima or minima. By analyzing it, they adjust the process using a trigonometric model to define the vertical shift (c), period and the amplitude (a). Learners comprehend the topic better when they are taught using real life scenarios. One example of it can be weather forecasting by utilizing sine and cosine functions. Students collect data about the weather, such as temperature, daylight hours, precipitations etc. and use this data for the trigonometric function and identify the weather patterns. With the help of the graph, they analyze hottest (maxima) and coldest (minima) days. This outcome can be used for identifying better planting and harvesting times, or suggestions for using energy more efficiently for seasonal temperature adjustment planning. During the project, students develop their problem solving skills through analytical reasoning, critical thinking, collaborative decision making, and creativity. Besides, they see the connection of math topics to real life and incorporate their knowledge from other subjects, such as geography, physics, biology and information technologies.

The respondent also emphasized the importance of group and pair work during math classes. According to the teacher, when students collaborate in math classes, the ones who are good at solving math problems help those who struggle and those who are more creative and think out of box contribute with their creative and critical thinking skills to team dynamics. Nevertheless, as highlighted by the respondent, it is not always possible to design the classes this way. The main reason behind this limitation is time constraints. As the school curriculum is rigid and the students have centralized graded assignments, it is impossible to design classes outside of the classroom so that the students can apply the content knowledge that they acquire during the classes in real-life situations. However, to actively involve the learners in the learning process, the teacher sets tasks which require data collection. He says that while collecting data for solving a problem, students encounter several obstacles and try to overcome them in teams. This enhances their teamwork, problem solving, and communication skills. The teacher sees his role in this situation as a guide and helps students when they cannot come up with any solutions. For instance, in a scenario where a cylindrical tank has a hole and water is leaking, students are given a task to model a function that relates the volume of water remaining in the tank to time. They should take the following steps in this task:

1. Begin by identifying the parameters and variables in the problem.
2. Using their knowledge of physics, students determine the volume of each water drop by applying the formula $V = \frac{m}{\rho}$, where V represents the volume, m is the mass, and ρ is the density of water.
3. Measure the time based on a constant rate of drop flow (e.g., 0.02 cm³ per second).
4. Create a table correlating the volume of water remaining in the tank with time intervals.
5. Indicate the data points on a graph to visually show the relationship between volume and
6. According to the behavior of the plotted graph, students can identify the type of function

7. Develop a mathematical model using the most suitable function based on their observations.

8. Assess the effectiveness of the model by checking if it accurately describes the data and makes reasonable predictions.

As can be seen, the process involves several steps, and the students may encounter challenges in selecting the appropriate model. In the initial steps of the project, the teacher provides guidance to some extent, but for subsequent projects, students independently choose and validate their models.

When it comes to the assessment methods in math classes, the respondent accentuated proof method as a non-traditional way of measuring student success. This method encompasses several important math skills. While implementing this approach, the learners are not introduced to the formula directly, rather they are presented with the problem and discover the formula while solving the problem. For example, in deriving the general term formula of an arithmetic sequence, $u_n = u_1 + d(n - 1)$ where u_1 is the first term, d is the common difference, and u_n is the n -th term, students are introduced not to the formula, but to the sequence itself. Through successive steps, they come to the formula by observing patterns in their calculations:

1. The second term u_2 is expressed as $u_1 + d$,
2. The third term u_3 is derived as $u_2 + d = u_1 + d + d = u_1 + 2d$,
3. Similarly, the fourth term $u_4 = u_3 + d = u_1 + 2d + d = u_1 + 3d$.

During the process, students observe that each term builds upon the previous one by adding d repeatedly. This leads them to identify that the coefficient of d in each term is one less than the term's index, ultimately leading to the general formula $u_n = u_1 + (n - 1)d$. Thus, by using induction deeper understanding of students is measured.

Regarding the projects assigned to students during the classes, the teacher stated that unfortunately, it is not always feasible to design them. The problem is related especially to the long-term projects since they require time, which is insufficient in the local curriculum because it is mainly exam oriented. Thus, to create math classes according to PBL model, there is need for fundamental changes in the school curriculum. This is a sad reality because PBL develops significant skills in learners, which is equally important for math classes as well. As the respondent highlights, in high school math classes the students mainly lack creative and critical thinking abilities and problem-solving skills, which is mainly due to the lack of their knowledge in math foundation. Therefore, the topics which are supposed to be covered in one or two academic hours (e.g. 3D shapes), take five or six hours to teach thereby creating problems with time to catch up with the rigid curriculum. For example, in the 11th-grade curriculum, there is a topic on planes and lines in three-dimensional (3D) space, as well as on 3D shapes such as cylinders, cones, prisms, and parallelepipeds. To fully grasp these concepts, students should first observe 3D shapes in real life and understand their mathematical representations. By linking tangible examples to their abstract mathematical forms,

students are better prepared to solve problems involving 3D shapes. For instance, a student may struggle to solve a problem involving a pyramid inscribed in a sphere if they cannot visualize the geometric relationships involved.

To see the situation from the students' perspective, we conducted focus group interviews with 10th grade students. According to the results of the interviews, the students describe their best experience in math classes when they are given a chance to express their opinions about what they think about math lessons and how they would like to see the classes in the future. The students also emphasized the positive impact of extra tasks and activities that are out of curriculum such as Olympiads preparation. They find it engaging and helpful to receive additional information which is not in the textbooks from the teacher. The students claim that some classes that are based on homework discussion truly help them to understand their mistakes thanks to the engagement of the whole class in the process and the teacher's explanation.

Regarding the challenges, the students face during solving math problems and the ways they deal with them; they state that professionalism of a teacher in employing various teaching methods immensely help them. Thus, math topics are comprehended better when explained not only with traditional instruction. They particularly highlighted the importance of peer and teamwork organized by the teacher and said that sometimes when the explanation of the teacher is not enough, they discuss with each other and see their problems clearly. The students also see this as a competition which encourages them to study hard in math classes. Moreover, the students state that their teacher frequently introduces authentic topics and explains the role of math problem solving skills in real life situations. However, like what was stated by the teacher during the interview, they also cannot apply what they learn in math classes outside of the classroom due to time constraints.

As an additional methodological tool, non-participant observations of math classes in grade 10 were conducted. The researchers particularly focused on the occurrence of PBL related activities or actions during the classes. The results of the analysis show that asking questions, interacting with each other, discussing, and problem solving were the main patterns and actions occurred in the classes. Although the class was not predominantly teacher oriented, the main interaction patterns during the observed sessions were either teacher and whole class or teacher and individual students. Nevertheless, the learners had some tasks that they completed in groups and discussed as a whole class. Several elements of PBL were evident in the process of teaching, i.e. the teacher was using real life problems and constantly making connections with the other subjects, such as geography, physics, and others. The learners were encouraged to share their ideas related to different solutions of the real-world mathematics problem. Overall, it can be stated that PBL elements existed in the observed classes, yet the whole class cannot be considered as a systematized PBL designed lesson.

Discussion

The research results can be divided into major themes, such as the alignment of a local curriculum with the PBL principles, teacher and students' perspectives regarding the implementation of real-life projects into math instruction, and the current situation in math classes.

The scrutiny of the math curriculum and course syllabus shows that they align with the major educational objectives described in the policy documents, such as Law on Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan and State Standards of General Education. The topics in math curriculum and syllabus are relevant to core principles of PBL methodology with their potential real-life application. The example topics, such as functions and trigonometry suggested by the respondent show how math concepts can be put into authentic context and engage students because of their relevance, applicability, and meaningfulness. This perfectly aligns with the ideas of Bilgin et al. (2015) and Hmelo-Silver (2004), who claim that projects make teaching and learning process relevant to real life. When students realize the applicability of the knowledge, they become more interested in the subject and increased motivation leads to long term knowledge retention. Although the curriculum and syllabus display that math classes can incorporate PBL into the instruction, we can see predominance of the traditional teaching method in the syllabus since the number of summative and exam-oriented assessments outweigh the formative and process-oriented evaluations. This discrepancy stresses the importance of adjustments in the curriculum and classroom instruction to successfully implement PBL approach.

From the math teacher's perspective, PBL involves potential to enhance learners' higher order thinking skills which leads to the development of problem solving, creative and critical thinking abilities. The examples provided by the teacher demonstrate how math topics can be put in real life context and deepen student motivation and foster 21st century skills which are in the focus of contemporary labor market. This finding echoes with the research done by Roh (2003). Also, the MUSIC model developed by Jones et al. (2016), can be relevant in our local context as well. Namely, as emphasized by the teacher, modeling quadratic functions for basketball analysis or utilizing trigonometric functions for weather forecasting enhances student engagement which in MUSIC model highlighted as usefulness and empowerment.

However, exam-oriented curriculum and limited time seem to be the main obstacles for effective PBL integration into the math classes. Our research results are consistent with the ideas analyzed in the literature. Existing research also highlights that putting math concepts in real life context in the teaching process is sometimes problematic for teachers and students because the curriculum mainly focuses on testing and does not promote deep learning (Ginsburg & Amit, 2008; Macmath, Roberts, Wallace, & Chi, 2009).

Similarly, the students in focus group interviews expressed the importance of authentic tasks and collaboration opportunities among the motivating factors in

math classes. As stated in the previous research, when learners see the relevance of the taught concepts to the real world and when they work in teams, the knowledge seems meaningful to them, and they feel more comfortable expressing themselves. This in turn positively affects their self-confidence and problem-solving skills (Bandura, 1997; Purzer, 2011). Furthermore, employing different teaching methods in math classes encourages learners and makes the knowledge acquisition more long term as opposed to only one traditional method where teacher is the only source of information.

Conducted classroom observations depicted occasional implementation of some PBL elements. The integration of real-life cases into math problems and connecting the topics with the other subjects showcased that the class becomes more engaging, and the learners develop different skills, such as analyzing, evaluating and problem solving. Yet this fragmented incorporation of PBL may not be sufficient to call the existing teaching approach a systematized PBL model. Although the teacher tried to encourage group and pair activities during the session, most part of the class was predominantly based on teacher-student interaction pattern. This case contradicts with the scholars' ideas that in the structured PBL driven classroom teacher is not the dominant figure, rather a facilitator, and the students are the ones who take the lead of the process, work actively in teams and solve real problems using taught math concepts (Mustaffa, Ismail, Tasir, & Mohamad Said, 2016).

Conclusion

Our results show that such elements of PBL as communication, collaboration, critical thinking, evaluation, problem-solving were evident in the math classes in the chosen sample, there are areas for improvement so that this method is utilized as a structured and systematized way of teaching. The difficulties for implementing PBL comprehensively in math classes articulated by the research participants echoes with the scholarly literature which indicates the traditional school curriculum as the main obstacle to PBL integration (Ginsburg & Amit, 2008; Macmath, Roberts, Wallace, & Chi, 2009). Furthermore, our analysis shows that the students feel more engaged in math classes when they sense the responsibility for their learning process and when the teacher encourages them to work in teams. Group works positively affect their critical thinking and problem-solving skills since they learn not only from the teacher but also from each other.

Hence, to fully benefit from PBL as a teaching methodology several crucial steps are to be taken. First, the existing curriculum should be revised so that it becomes more flexible in terms of incorporating authentic problems and balance summative assessments with formative ones to ensure more competence-based and application-oriented lessons rather than exam centered. Also, to deliver an effective PBL approach professional development trainings need to be organized to equip teachers with the skills to design authentic projects aligned with the curriculum and standards.

While our research sheds light on the possibility of PBL integration into the local math curriculum, it also creates opportunities for future research. Further

studies can include more schools or grade levels to have a broader comprehension of the PBL practice in local schools. Also, the sample size can be increased to employ quantitative study with the purpose of generalizing the findings. Comparative studies on traditional methods and PBL can be conducted as experiment research and results can display the level of student engagement, academic achievement, and problem-solving skills.

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